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**QUALITY OF NEIGHBOURHOOD, ATTITUDE TOWARDS POLICE AND
DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AS FACTORS INFLUENCING FEAR OF CRIME IN
PERI-URBAN COMMUNITIES IN OYO STATE**

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of quality of neighbourhood, attitude towards police and demographic variables on fear of crime in peri-urban communities in Egbeda LGA of Oyo state. The study was an ex-post facto design. Three hundred and sixteen (316) participants were selected for the study through multi-stage sampling technique from Olorunsogo toll gate, Ajia, Bolorunduro, Ifedapo and Ajule municipalities located in Egbeda LGA. Descriptive statistics, t-test for independent analysis and multiple regression analysis significance were used to analyse the data at 0.05 level significance. Results demonstrated that residents in high quality neighbourhoods significantly reported higher fear of crime. There was statistically significant effect of attitude towards police on fear of crime. Age, education and gender predicted fear of crime respectively among residents of Ibadan. It was concluded that good Quality of neighbourhood, and having positive attitude towards police affects residents' level of fear of crime among the residents living in peri-urban communities in the Ibadan metropolis. Thus, it was recommended that the institutionalization of community policing was advocated for the urban centres in order to reduce the incidence of crime and problems of fear of crime among the citizens.

Keywords: Fear of crime, Quality of neighbourhood, Attitude towards police, Demographic variables

Introduction

Fear is the subjective feeling which surrounds individuals of being a victim of crime in an area with prevalent criminal activities (Ayoyo, 2014). Vanderveen (2006) refers to fear of crime as the sense of personal insecurity in the community or an emotional response to possible violence that could arise from criminal activities in the environment. Ayoyo (2014) allege that contemporary manifestation of fear of crime is now a peculiar public attitudes and responses to crime. These concerns among the public is manifested in building of high fences, security warnings and signs not to trespass, use of surveillance devices, employment of neighborhood watchman etc. (Ayoyo, 2014). This led to the emergence of various form of neighborhood security associations, street gates, installation of burglary proofs on windows and doors in order to protect against falling victim of crime (Aborisade, 2017). Reports indicate that as high as 50% of Nigerians patronize the services of these community-based security operatives for their protection from criminal attacks (Ayoyo, 2014).

Of great interest is the concern about increasing fear of crime and its negative effect on the psyche of the residents in urban centres in Nigeria. Though, criminal activities are believed to be on the increase, statistics revealed that these perceptions appear to be overblown thus increasing the level of palpable fear among the residents. Individuals who fear crime often feel depressed and unhappy leading to psychological discomfort which reduces subjective wellbeing and is associated with poor health (Faeth & Kittler, 2017). As avoidance is a common response to fear, fearful individuals not only restrict their outdoor activities but also make them over sensitive (Faeth & Kittler, 2017). These results in mistrust towards others and limit the ability to form social ties leading disruptive social behaviour such as extra judicial behaviour, mob actions and jungle justice. Further, fear of crime reduces their well-being (Sulemana, 2015).

Some of the sources adduced for the palpable fear of crime and victimization is the neighbourhood quality, attitude towards police and demographic characteristics. Particularly important in this regard in explaining these trends in urban fear of crime is the Shaw and McKay (1942) social disorganization theory. Shaw and McKay proposed three structural dimensions of neighbourhoods were most important central factors explaining variation in crime: the socio-economic status of the area; the level of residential mobility; and the degree of ethnic heterogeneity (McCrea, Shyy, Western, & Stimson, 2005). Specifically, they linked rapid population change within low socio-economic status and ethnically diverse neighbourhoods to a breakdown of law and order. This breakdown limits the ability of communities to control the behaviour of both residents and outsiders, prompting increased delinquency and other forms of normatively deviant behavior (McCrea et. al., 2005). Thus, a major source of fear of crime, urban context has long informed fear of crime studies.

Urban areas plagued by higher crime rates than nonurban areas, coupled with a weakened sense of solidarity, may consequently be characterized by more fearful behaviour and attitudes. Research documents that urban residents have greater fear or crime than nonurban residents, and within urban environments fear of crime increases with city size (Snedker, 2010). Conditions in the environment, especially in one's immediate environment, may increase fear through particular cues or in a constellation of related cues. In an urban setting, individuals are navigating

both in their own neighbourhoods and through other urban spaces. Disorder or incivilities can be considered visible “signs of crime” indicating that dangerous elements are present and social control mechanisms within the neighbourhood have broken down (Snedker, 2010).

More recently, research suggests that it may also be important to consider the neighbourhood context in attempting to understand patterns of fear of crime in urban centres (Ayoyo, 2014). The environment or the context plays a large part in determining levels of vulnerability (Goodey, 2005). Doran and Lees (2005) claim that areas characterized by poor natural surveillance provide opportunities for disorder or crime to get a foothold. Allen (2006) found that those living in inner-city and council estates and areas with high levels of victimization and social/physical disorder (graffiti, vandalism) were generally more fearful. Contrary to these in the Nigeria context it is the high-quality neighbourhoods than the poor neighbourhoods that get attacked more due to poor security network based on anecdotal evidences. There has not been any formal research conducted to determine the assessment level of fear of crime in local communities either high or poor neighbourhood quality in the Ibadan metropolis.

Police presence and community- related interactions with the police have also been found to reduce fear of crime (Snedker, 2010). Klein, Webb and DiSanto (1978) described attitude toward the police as the overall opinion the citizens expresses relative to police fairness, courtesy, honesty, understanding, intelligence, knowledge of the job and concern for the public. Positive public attitudes toward the police have been identified to make crime prevention and control easier for police to accomplish. Fairness and positive treatment by law enforcement are important aspects of the public’s perception of police as a legitimate force (Lewis, 2016). Nigeria experienced an undemocratic police force in Nigeria (Hills, 2012). Nigeria is believed to be served by a police force that is despotic, corrupt, and resistant to change.

The police whose duty it is to provide security have consistently admitted that they are handicapped because of a combination of factors among which are: lack of resources, poor government support and poor conditions of service resulting in ill-motivated, ill-trained and ill-equipped workforce. Reflecting broadly, reaction time can be affected by unavailability of vehicles to be dispatched to a crime scene, possibly overstretched by multiple incidents and having no standby capacity to react timely (Obarisiagbon & Omagie, 2018). Thus, there slow response, non- proactive police and corruption have been implicated in the negative attitude towards the Nigerian police and subsequent heighten level of fear crime (Obarisiagbon & Omagie, 2018). However, this trend has not been confirmed in empirical literature. A study suggested that those who have lower fear of crime perceive the police to be more effective than those with greater fear (Dowler, 2003). Despite these findings, the relationship between fear of crime and police perceptions is understudied.

Looking at socio-demographic variables associated with fear of crime, age and gender remain consistent overtime (Snedker, 2010). The consistent finding regarding fear of crime and gender is that women are more fearful than men despite being less likely to be victimized. Lee (2007) stresses the significance gender has as an independent variable in fear of crime research, and points out that empirical study have repeatedly found that women are more fearful of crime than men and yet are less likely to become the victims of most categories of serious crime. It has been suggested by Jefferson and Hollway (2000) that fear of crime means different things to men and

women. While men are more likely to be most fearful of assault, women are more concerned about sexually-motivated attacks. Nevertheless, fear trends between the genders are generally not reflected by likelihood of victimization.

Moore and Shepherd (2007) acknowledge a shift in findings about fear and age. They claim that while previous research highlighted elderly people as the most fearful in society, more recent studies have started to report the opposite. Older people who are wheelchair bound or disabled may be fearful knowing they are powerless to retaliate. Therefore, this study assess residents' perceptions of neighborhood quality and its relationship with fear of crime. The main objective of this study is to investigate the influence of quality of neighbourhood, attitude police and demographic variables on fear of crime in Oyo state. The aims and objectives were achieved through the specific objectives such as:

1. To examine whether quality of neighbourhood will influence fear of crime
3. To determine whether attitude towards police will influence fear of crime
4. To find out whether residents demographic variables (e.g age, gender and education) will relatively predict fear of crime.

Methodology

This study was an ex-post facto design. A total of three hundred and sixteen (316) participants were selected for the study. The respondents were sampled from Olorunsogo toll gate Zone which include, Akinjole (Zone 1 to 3) and Bolorunpelu In the Ajia Zone area areas sampled include; IyanaAjia (Zone 1) Mobolohunduro (Zone 2) Araro , and Ajia community landlord and landladies' association. For the Egbeda Area Zone, places sampled include, Bolorunduro, Ifedapo (Zone 1-2), Temidire, Irewumi, Olugbojo, Sokan, Tanmo, Temidire , Carpenter And Ajule Landlords and Landladies Associations. A structured questionnaire was used in data collection in the study. Fear of crime was measured using 10 items scale developed by the Ferraro (1995). Responses ranged from not being afraid at all (1) to being very afraid (10). The reliability was 0.86.

Neighbourhood quality was measured eight-item scale developed by Flanagan and Longmire (1995) Items are structured on five-point scale Likert-type response format ranging from (1 = "strongly disagree", 2 = "disagree", 3 = "undecided", 4 "agree", 5 ="strongly agree"). The scale had a Cronbach's Alpha of .843. Scores above the mean score denotes high quality neighbourhood, while scores below the mean score denotes low quality neighbourhood. Cronbach's a coefficient for the total measure is 0.70 was recorded by this study. Attitude toward the police was measured using the Perception of Police Scale developed by Chow, (2011). The questions were general in nature in that they asked about respondents' overall attitudes toward the police. Respondents were asked how much they agree or disagree (1=strongly agree, 2=agree, 3=neutral, 4=disagree, 5=strongly disagree) with statements." Scores were then summed, higher scores mean more positive attitudes toward police. The scale obtained a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.84 in the current study.

Permissions were obtained from the authorities and land lord associations in the areas used for the study. The self-report questionnaires were used to collect data from the participants in the study. The participants were informed of the purposes and/or objectives of the study, and its

seriousness. Direction on how to complete the questionnaires was given and, they were encouraged to be truthful as possible in their responses. Honesty in its completeness was highly and continuously emphasized during the course of administration. The researcher assured some participants that their questionnaires would not be personally identified. Finally, those participants who were willing to participate in the study were encouraged to fill the questionnaire correctly. The collected data was first check for its adequacy and then analyzed using t-test for independent analysis and multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Result

Hypothesis One: High level of Quality of neighbourhood would significantly influence high fear of crime than residents with low level of Quality of neighborhood among residents of Ibadan.

Table 1: Summary table of T-test showing a comparison of coefficient test of residents with high and low levels of Quality of neighborhoods on fear of crime of Ibadan

	Quality of neighbourhood	N	Mean	S.D	t	df	Sig.
Fear of crime	Low	173	34.36	9.04	-4.231	314	.000
	High	143	38.69	9.05			

From the Table 1, it was observed that there was significant influence of Quality of neighbourhood on fear of crime among residents of Ibadan. Residents in high quality neighborhoods’ significantly reported higher fear of crime $t(314) = -4.23, p < .001$. Therefore, the first hypothesis which stated that, resident with high level of Quality of neighbourhood would significantly have negative effect on fear of crime with low level of Quality of neighbourhood among residents of Ibadan was partially supported.

Hypothesis Two: The negative attitude towards police would significantly report more fear of crime than residents with positive attitude towards police of Ibadan.

Table 2: Summary table of T-test showing a comparison of coefficient test of residents with high and low levels of attitude towards police on fear of crime of Ibadan

Dependent variable	Attitude towards police	N	Mean	S.D	t	df	Sig.
Fear of crime	Negative	184	40.804	7.32	-12.31	314	.000
	Positive	132	30.075	8.07			

From the Table 2, it was observed that there was statistically significant effect of attitude towards police on fear of crime $t(314) = 12.31, p < .001$. Therefore, the third hypothesis which stated that, resident with negative attitude towards police would significantly report more fear of crime than residents with positive attitude towards police among residents of Ibadan was fully supported.

Hypothesis Three: Demographic variables (Age, gender and Educational Qualification) would jointly and significantly predict fear of crime.

Table 3: Summary of multiple regression analysis showing the influence of Age, education and gender on fear of crime among residents of Ibadan

Variable	β	t-value	Sig	R	R^2	F	P
Age	.18	4.21	<.01				
Educational Qualification	.05	.93	>.05				
Gender	.55	10.38	<.01	.63	.39	68.68	<.001

The result in Table 3, revealed that respondents scores on residents age, education and gender jointly explains 39% of the change in variation observed in the fear of crime respectively among residents of Ibadan ($R^2 = 0.39$; $F(3,313) = 8.68$, $p < .001$). The result also demonstrated that independently, Age ($\beta = .18$, $t = 4.21$, $p < .01$) and gender ($\beta = .55$, $t = 10.38$, $p < .01$) predicted fear of crime while Educational Qualification ($\beta = .05$, $t = 0.93$, $p > .05$) was not significant. Therefore, the third hypothesis which posited that age and gender would independently and jointly predict fear of crime was supported.

Discussion

The first hypothesis which stated that resident with high Quality neighbourhood would significantly report lesser fear of crime than residents with low level Quality neighbourhood among residents of Ibadan was partially supported. High quality neighborhood induced higher fear of crime. This finding is in contrast with Doran and Lees (2005) who reported poor quality areas reported more crimes. In the same vein disagree with The Allen (2006) found that those living poor quality urban centres were generally more fearful of criminal victimisation.

The second hypothesis which postulated that residents with negative attitude towards police would significantly report more fear of crime than residents with positive attitude towards police among residents of Ibadan was fully supported. The finding is in agreement Dowler, (2003) that lower fear of crime perceive the police to be more effective than those with greater fear.

The third hypothesis which posited that Age, gender and Educational Qualification would independently and jointly predict fear of crime was supported. Age and gender predicted fear of crime. This finding supports the findings of Allen (2006) which demonstrated that women were fear fearful of property crimes than men. In the same vein the study of Ramsay (1989) which reveals that greater percentage of women were fearful of crime than men. The findings are in contrast with Allen (2006) which found that young men are more fearful of automobile theft than the older residents. However, the findings support Moore and Shepherd (2007) which demonstrated that elderly people as the most fearful of crime as adolescents.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn as a result of the finding of this study: It was demonstrated that good Quality of neighbourhood, having positive attitude towards police affects residents' level of fear of crime among the residents living in peri-urban communities in the Ibadan metropolis. The results of the study provide insights into the extent and pattern of public

perceptions and fear of crime. The scope of the study was limited to people living in Ibadan metropolis. Future studies should consider much larger sample size. Further studies in understanding the influence of Quality of neighbourhood, attitude towards police on fear of crime in Ibadan becomes important. To guarantee regular reconnaissance visual deterrents and camouflage for potential lawbreakers offer the most security against wrongdoing. In this way, inhabitants ought to guarantee that visual surveillance, for example, trees; bushes, blossom beds don't hinder their vision of the prompt condition, and don't make zones of disguise where interlopers could cover up to perform odious exercises.

Recommendation

1. The most modern of electronic observing gadgets such as Closed Circuit TV (CCTV) should be introduced.
2. Vacant local location of the towns are generally left high rate of relinquished properties, abandoned structures just as rundown structures and less undeveloped plots of land that has developed trees and brambles. All these could be fort for crooks and criminals.
3. Government should approach the proprietors of these properties to revamp, total and involve or make their properties useful inside a sensible given timeframe. There is additionally requirement for the networks policing to build up more police posts and watch groups.
4. Psycho-education stakeholders should be offered to teach people in general about crime, and fear of crime have a superior comprehension of their hazard.

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